

Wind and Ice Loads on Transmission Structures: A State of the Art Review

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Abstract:

Climactic loads imposed on transmission conductors include ice, wind and ice concurrent with wind. Structural reliability under these loads depends on the statistical variation of applied loads and associated resistances. Analytical treatment for combined wind and ice effects is difficult given the different probability distribution functions of ice thickness and wind speeds. Existing design codes and guidelines are somewhat inconsistent in defining what actually applies for low and extreme winds. This paper reviews the present state of the art in research on wind speed and ice thickness distributions, associated risks, forecasting models, MRIs (recurrence

intervals), field-based weather records and databases. The main inference from this study is that low to moderate winds should be modeled with a probability distribution different from that of extreme or hurricane winds. Reasonable reliability design procedures for combined ice and wind loads can be developed for utility structures with proper statistical assumptions.

Keywords: *distribution, ice, probability, reliability, transmission, variation, wind.*

Introduction

The performance of electrical transmission structures and lines is defined by the environmental and mechanical loads sustained by the system. Climactic loads on transmission conductors include radial ice, wind and ice concurrent with wind (see Figure 1), in addition to temperature-related effects. Structural reliability under these loads depends on the statistical variation of applied loads and

resistances, as reflected in the coefficients of variation (COV) for ice thickness and wind speed. Accurate analytical treatment for *concurrent* ice and wind is challenging because of the different probability distribution functions of ice and wind speeds. Some typical, code-mandated load and weather cases, comprising ice and wind, for the design of a transmission line are shown in Table 1.

V = Vertical Load effects due to bare wire weight with or without Ice
 T = Transverse Load effects due to wind on bare wire or iced wire

Figure 1. Ice and Wind Loads on Conductors

Table 1. Typical NESC Weather and Load Cases

No.	Weather / Load Case	Temperature (°F)	Radial Ice Thickness (in)*	Wind Speed (mph) *	Parameters for COV
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
1	Heavy Loading District (NESC 250B)	0	0.50	40	Ice and Wind
2	Medium Loading District (NESC 250B)	15	0.25	40	Ice and Wind
3	Light Loading District (NESC 250B)	30	0	60	Wind alone
4	Extreme Wind (NESC 250C)	60	0	100 *	Wind alone
5	Extreme Ice (non-NESC)	32	1.0 **	0	Ice alone
6	Concurrent Ice with Wind (NESC 250D)	15	0.50 to 0.75	30 to 40	Ice and Wind

Note: * location-specific; ** values of over 2 inches and more have been recorded; 1 inch = 25.4 mm, 1 mph = 1.61 kph 1 C = 0.555 F – 32

Transmission and distribution structures in the United States are designed on the basis of Load and Resistance Factor Design (LRFD) where the statistical variability of applied loads is matched with that of the resistance to reduce the possibility of failure. This approach is also called Reliability-Based Analysis and Design (or RBAD) since it provides a specified level of design reliability based on the Return Period (RP) or Mean Recurrence Interval (MRI) of climactic events such as high winds and ice storms. The default MRI per Manual 74 (American Society of Civil Engineers, 2019) is

100 years, although larger periods up to 300 years are often used in special circumstances. All electric utility overhead design in the United States is also governed by the IEEE’s NESC or National Electrical Safety Code (National Electrical Safety Code, 2023) which is basically a “safety” code but draws heavily from ASCE Standards (American Society of Civil Engineers, 2022).

For a broader understanding of RBAD, the reader is referred to the abundant literature available on the topic (Ang, & Tang, 1984;

Kalaga, & Yenumula, 2016; Kharmanda, & El-Hami, 2016). The standards of reliable performance of wood utility pole structures are discussed in ASCE Manual of Practice 111 (American Society of Civil Engineers, 2006) and ANSI (American National Standards Institute, 2022). RUS-USDA (Rural Utilities Services, 2015) gives design guidelines for rural transmission lines funded by the US Government.

However, the analytical process is complicated when opinions are varied on how to define low-to-moderate and extreme (hurricane) wind speeds, and what distributions are to be adopted for reasonably good results. Loading guidelines (American Society of Civil Engineers, 2019) are still based on older 2016 standards while NESC is already updated in 2023. Further, some researchers assume ice loads follow a Normal (Gaussian), Pareto or a GEV (Generalized Extreme Value) distribution; wind speeds, depending on magnitude, are assumed to follow a Weibull, Lognormal or an Extreme Value (EV) Type 1 distribution. Latest updates to codes show recognition of climate change considerations, higher MRIs and adjusted wind speeds, although the updates are not in the same year. The codes are also inconsistent about the influence of parameters that affect how wind speed is evaluated objectively (terrain, structure elevation, location relative to coast, measurement periods, direction of action). The availability of reliable *measured* ice and wind speed records is also a significant issue since the size of the database affects the quality of the predictive nature of winds and associated forces. Recorded data (from weather stations) covers about 100 years and values above that are deduced either by extrapolation or by Monte Carlo Simulations (MCS), using a specific mean and COV.

This paper presents a review of the current state of the art in assessing ice and wind loads on transmission conductors and structures. Previous research studies, including adopted statistical distributions and simulations, are briefly discussed for situations that include both ice and wind, together and separately.

Statistical Perspectives

Reliability Index

The traditional definition of a Reliability Index β for a *normally distributed variable* is:

$$\beta = (M_R - M_W) / \text{sqrt}(\sigma_R^2 + \sigma_W^2) \quad (1)$$

where:

M_R = Mean value of Resistance at pole Ground Line

M_W = Mean Value of Applied Load Effects at Ground Line

σ_R = Standard Deviation of Resistance = $(\text{COV}_R) * (M_R)$

σ_W = Standard Deviation of Load Effect = $(\text{COV}_W) * (M_W)$

COV_R = Coefficient of Variation of Resistance

COV_W = Coefficient of Variation of Load Effect

Load effects can be reactions (bending moment, shear and axial forces) at the pole or structure base due to vertical and horizontal loads on the conductors, wind on pole surface and due to applicable wire tensions at locations of line angles. Equation (1) is not applicable if any of the two variables is non-Normal. That is, it must be modified appropriately to allow joint use of parameters of different statistical distributions.

Wind Speed and Pressure

The wind pressure w in *psf* on a transmission structure corresponding to a wind speed V is (National Electrical Safety Code, 2023):

$$w = 0.00256 * V^2 k_z G_{RF} C_d I \quad (2)$$

where:

V = wind speed in miles per hour, 3-second gust measured at 33 ft. (10 m) above ground

$k_{z\zeta}$ = Velocity Pressure Exposure Coefficient (depends on pole height above ground)

G_{RF} = Gust Response Factor (depends on pole height above ground)

C_d = Shape Factor (1.0 for round objects such as poles, 1.6 for flat surfaces)

I = Importance Factor (assumed to be 1.0)

The wind pressure parameters in NESC are based on Exposure Category C which is open terrain with scattered obstructions. All values refer to a 100 year MRI (American Society of Civil Engineers, 2019).

The variables in Equation 2 are V , $k_{z\zeta}$ and G_{RF} whose typical COV's are given as follows by Ellingwood and Tekie (1999) and Simiu et al. (2012).

$COV_{k_{z\zeta}}$ 0.16 (Normal Distribution)

$COV_{G_{RF}}$ 0.11 (Normal Distribution)

COV_V 0.12 (typical) (EV Type 1 Distribution for 50 years MRI)

0.131 (EV Type 1 Distribution) for 100 years MRI (extrapolated)

Resultant COV combining all variables = $COV_R = \sqrt{[COV_{kz}^2 + COV_{GRF}^2 + 4COV_{V50}^2]}$ (3)

Equation (3) assumes that the variables are uncorrelated.

The above-mentioned research studies also indicated that a Type 1 Distribution of largest wind speed values is more appropriate than Type 2 given its thinner upper tail and considered the most common cumulative probability distribution function (CDF) for wind speed analyses worldwide.

Ice and Wind Variations

The thickness of radial ice on conductors, which varies from 1/4" (6 mm) to 1.5" (38 mm) depending upon the location, is generally considered to follow a Normal (or Gaussian) Distribution with a COV about 0.18 per NCHRP (2003) and Joffre and Laurila (1988). However, wind speeds are usually considered amenable to a Weibull defined by scale and size parameters or an Extreme Value Type 1 (EVT1), defined by a mean and COV. It is generally understood that Weibull is applicable only for low-to-moderate wind speeds (Shi, et al., 2021; Vickery, et al., 2000). The EVT1 is suitable for modeling land surface high wind speeds and is simple to adopt if values mean and COV are known. The characteristics of these two distributions are available in any standard textbook on statistics or applications of probability theory: Holmes (2017), Simiu and Scanlan (1986), Ang and Tang (1984). Literature indicates that the COV of high wind speeds in USA varies from 0.10 to 0.13, depending on the MRI. Table 2 shows the numerical values of the two variables and their assumed variation.

Table 2. Variables and Probability Distributions

No.	Property Name	Range	Typical COV	Probability Distribution
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
1	Radial Ice Thickness t (in) *	0.25 to 1.50 **	0.18	Normal Generalized Extreme Value
2	Wind Speed V (mph) *	30 to 150 #	0.09	Weibull Lognormal Extreme Value Type 1

Note: * location-specific; ** values of over 2 inches and more have been recorded; #measured 33 ft. (10 m) above ground; 1 inch = 25.4 mm, 1 mph = 1.61 kph

Combined Ice and Wind Studies

We will now look at the literature available on concurrent ice and wind on conductors.

Savadjiev and Farzaneh (2003) studied combined wind and ice occurrences in Quebec area of Canada for reliabilities at 150 and 500 year MRIs. They assumed that initial wind speed distributions concurrent with ice are best described by a Weibull Distribution. A reduction factor for wind speed was introduced. It was observed that the average COV of wind speeds was about 0.136. They suggested that combined wind and ice loads with a prescribed return period (MRI) should be calculated combining the largest extreme ice thickness with a reduced wind speed occurring simultaneously during icing events.

Ma, Dai and Pang (2020) modeled extreme wind speed and ice accretion using both Weibull as well as a Pareto Distribution and concluded that, during icing rain, concurrent wind speed significantly impacts the reliability of electric grids. ASCE 111 (American Society of Civil Engineers, 2006) also states that ice load on wires concurrent with wind is considered a critical design condition. This is because accreted ice not only increases gravity load but also expands the projected area of the wire affecting the drag coefficient for wind.

Jafari and Baghal (2022) studied reduction factors for combined ice and wind loading for MRIs of 50, 150 and 500 years at select locations in Iran. Table 3 shows the distributions and approximate parameter values of basic climactic events. A Weibull Distribution was assumed for both maximum ice and maximum wind speed.

Table 3. Basic Climactic Events, Probability Distributions

No.	Event Variable	Assumed Probability Distribution	Values
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
1	Icing Event Occurrence	Poisson	12.2 events per year
2	Duration of Icing Event (hours)	Exponential	Mean = 13.8
3	Maximum Ice Thickness in each event (mm)	Weibull	Shape Parameter $k = 1.41$ Scale Parameter $c = 25.2$
4	Maximum Daily Wind Speed (mps)	Weibull	Shape Parameter $k = 0.41$ Scale Parameter $c = 0.016$

Note: 1 inch = 25.4 mm, 1 mps = 3.281 fps = 2.237 mph

Rezaei et al. (2015) studied the vulnerability of lattice transmission towers subjected to unbalanced ice loads in 3 cardinal directions and introduced fragility curves based on Statistical Learning Theory (SLT). The study indicated that wind speed, wind direction and *ice accumulation rate* have a direct effect on the fragility or failure curves. Halder (2007) studied actual ice accumulation with concurrent wind measured at chosen locations in Northeastern Canada and observed ice thicknesses over 50 mm (2 inches), about 4 times that of the assumed design thickness.

Yang, et al. (2020) discussed a joint wind-ice probability distribution based on the Binary Copula Function and field data of wind speed and ice thickness from Southwest China.

Concurrent wind and ice were analyzed and fitted using Gumbel, Weibull and GEV Distributions. MRIs of 30, 50 and 100 years are used to assess the models (see Table 5). It is concluded that GEV model matches the characteristics of *both* wind speed and ice intensity. However, the maximum wind speed used in the study is about only 7.5 mps (16.7 mph) while the maximum ice thickness was about 18.7 mm ($\frac{3}{4}$ in.) indicating low to moderate wind and ice. Similar studies were made by Liang, et al. (2023) for lattice towers with the conclusion that GEV and EVT1 performs better for ice thickness and wind speed, respectively (see Table 6).

Arriaga (2020) studied joint wind and ice effects on transmission lines in mountainous terrains of

Canada by characterizing the hazard by simulating 500 years of icing events from fitted probability distributions. The study also considered the wind-induced vibrations on iced asymmetrical conductors (galloping) which generated extra tension at the support points on the structure. It is suggested that uncertainties while dealing with joint ice and wind hazard can be reduced by quantifying its contribution to the total tension transmitted to the structure.

Sheng, Tang and Hong (2023) suggested that the Gumbel Distribution is adequate for regions of large ice accretion while the Lognormal Distribution is appropriate for areas of low to negligible ice accretion. The study also concluded that for a 50-year MRI, the statistical characteristics of concurrent ice and maximum

wind are different from maximum wind speed alone.

Rossi, et al. (2020) studied the combined effects of wind and atmospheric ice on overhead transmission lines. One interesting result of the study is the development of a Risk Assessment Matrix (see Figure 2) where the risk associated with each combination of ice and wind is defined in terms of the *Likelihood* of the case and *Impact* on the overall transmission line system. The Likelihood parameter is deduced from the yearly average number of hours ‘n’ of occurrence of the event, varying from 10 hours to 200 hours. The Impact parameter is calculated from the percentage ratio R between the horizontal component of the additional tension due to galloping and the horizontal component of the design load. R is noted to vary from 5% to 30%.

		Impact			
		Low	Medium	High	Very High
L i k e l i h o o d	Frequent	4 Moderate	8 Major	12 Severe	16 Severe
	Probable	3 Minor	6 Moderate	9 Major	12 Severe
	Possible	2 Minor	4 Minor	6 Moderate	8 Major
	Rare	1 Minor	2 Minor	3 Minor	4 Moderate

Likelihood		Impact	
Rare	n < 10 hours	Low	R = 5%
Possible	10 h < n < 50 h	Medium	5% < R < 10%
Probable	50 h < n < 200 h	High	10% < R < 30%
Frequent	n > 200 hours	Very High	R > 30%

Figure 2. Risk Assessment Matrix

Distributions

Jagger, Elsner and Niu (2001) studied dynamic probability models for hurricane winds assuming a Weibull Distribution (WD) for maximum wind speed due to tropical storms. Justus, et al. (1978) suggested using a WD for fitting observed wind speed frequency data and included ways of estimating the two parameters associated with WD based on anemometer height at which wind

is measured. They suggested simple relationships between shape factor k and wind speed V .

Shi, et al. (2021) assessed various wind speed distribution models and the goodness of fit with measured data. The Weibull curves for low and moderate winds are almost similar except that the plot for moderate winds has a longer tail. The study observed that the 2-parameter WD is not suitable for all wind regimes in nature and is less

effective at low wind speeds. Another significant inference from this study is that extreme wind speeds have no effect on WD parameters and once the speed exceeds a given threshold, the Weibull model is no longer applicable. In such cases, the practical alternative is to use the Extreme Value Distributions (EVD) such as Gumbel, Inverse Weibull, and the Generalized Extreme Value (GEV). The EVD is noted to be more accurate than a WD in estimating the occurrence of extreme wind speeds since the tail is thicker than the WD.

He, Monahan, Jones (2010) studied surface wind speeds using a 2-parameter Weibull Distribution and using data from 720 weather stations in North America spread over 20 years. The study concluded that a WD is a reasonable first-order model for daytime surface wind speeds over all surface types although at some locations the behavior is distinctly non-Weibull. However, for night time winds, the WD is different in terms of skewness.

Al-Temimi (2022) presented a detailed discussion on how to evaluate the Weibull scale (k) and shape (c) parameters, using both graphical and analytical methods. Among the analytical methods, the simplest is the SDM (Standard Deviation Method) and is useful where only the mean wind speed and standard deviation (or COV) are available. With SDM, the scale and shape parameters can be estimated from the mean and standard deviation. When the scale parameter becomes 2.0, the Weibull becomes a Raleigh Distribution. When the shape parameter becomes 1.0, it becomes an Exponential Distribution.

Tijerina and Monarrez (2021) discussed application of WD from a stress-strength and Reliability perspective with the shape parameter varying from 0.5 to 3.0. A series of mathematical relationships are proposed to numerically evaluate reliability based on number of observations.

Kulkarni and Powar (2011) suggested a Normal transformation for Weibull Distribution when the shape parameter is known. This is based on two key features of the Normal Distribution, namely symmetry and tail behavior. It is

observed that the proposed approximation performs well even for small sample sizes and small shape parameters. Tanaka and Ichikawa (1983) put forward an approximate formula for the coefficient of variation of a Weibull Distribution as a function of the shape parameter (SP).

$$COV = SP^{-0.93} \approx \frac{1}{SP} \quad 1 \leq SP \leq 50 \quad (4)$$

Conversely: $SP = COV^{-1.075}$

The relative error of Equation 4 is less than 3% in most cases.

Rick Haynes (2011) proposed an approximate method of transforming a Weibull Distribution by linking the scale parameter λ to the shape parameter k as follows.

$$\lambda = 10^{-0.623+1.00410(k)} \quad (5)$$

Sedliackova, et al. (2022) analyzed wind speed data collected over 11 years in Slovakia for low-to-moderate winds less than 31 mph (13.85 mps). They observed that the seasonal value of the Weibull shape parameter ranged from 1.474 to 1.607 (average: 1.546) while the scale parameter varied from 2.488 to 3.010 mps (average: 2.726 mps). Another inference is that wherever the shape parameter is less than 2, it indicates variable winds.

Other Studies

Rosowsky and Huang (2000) studied wind load reliability of building frames using ASCE 7 (2022) provisions. Along with other studies Ellingwood, and Tekie, (1999), they suggested that for roofs of typical low-rise buildings, all factors appearing in the wind pressure equation can be treated as Normal Random Variables with values shown in Table 4. This study also indicated that the COV of maximum wind speeds at coastal locations in North Carolina, South Carolina and Florida is about 0.135.

Table 4. Statistics for ASCE Wind Load Factors for Buildings

No.	Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	COV
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
1	Exposure Factor K_z	0.80	0.12	0.15
2	Gust Factor G	0.82	0.08	0.098
3	Topographic Factor K_{zt}	1.0	-	-
4	Importance Factor I	1.0	-	-
5	Directionality Factor	0.89	0.14	0.157

Markee (1963) studied wind speed fluctuations at various sampling intervals (¼ hour, ½ hour and 1 hour) at two urban locations at a reference height of 33 ft. (10m) and deduced that using a range to depict wind speeds is not a good indicator of standard deviation of wind speed.

Dookie, et al., (2018) evaluated various wind speed probability distribution models including Birnbaum-Sanders, Exponential, Gamma, Generalized Extreme Value (GEV), Generalized Pareto, Nakagami, Normal, Rayleigh Distribution (RD) and Weibull Distributions. Although the study was intensive with respect of number of distributions investigated, the average wind speed is around 11.6 mph which is very low. The main conclusion was that both WD and RD are poor choices for wind speed models and that evaluation of wind speeds is a location-specific activity and is unique for each location.

Murnane and Elsner (2012) discussed maximum wind speeds, hurricane and losses due to damages. All three major areas of continental USA are considered: Gulf Coast, Florida and East Coast. They suggested that the relationship between wind speed and financial loss is

exponential and that losses at landfall increase with wind speed at the rate of 5% for every meter per sec.

Xie, et al. (2006) developed a real-time hurricane wind speed forecasting model by using Holland asymmetric effects, the NOAA (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration) and NHC (National Hurricane Center) guidelines. This model is validated via the 2003 and 2004 Atlantic and Gulf of Mexico hurricanes. Results showed that the accuracy of forecasting is a direct function of the model’s ability to quantify the uncertainty in any climactic occurrence.

Malmquist (2000) studied hurricane wind speed estimating models along the southern and eastern coasts of USA. This model is based on latitude and longitude of the location along the coast and the maximum wind speed of a hurricane crossing the coast line. Hurricane landfall probabilities are also used in the model. The model estimates the probability of a hurricane exceeding 50 mps (112 mph) which is close to a Category 3 storm within a 95% confidence interval.

Table 5. Distribution Parameters for Wind Speed and Ice Thickness

No.	Distribution Type	Sample Type	Mean	Scale Factor	Shape Factor	KS Test
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
1	Gumbel	Wind Speed (mph)	12.46	6.76		0.30
		Ice Thickness (in.)	0.56	0.26		0.37
2	Weibull	Wind Speed (mph)	16.78	6.98		0.32
		Ice Thickness (in.)	0.74	0.17		0.30
3	GEV (Generalized Extreme Value)	Wind Speed (mph)	14.85	5.57	0.76	0.20
		Ice Thickness (in.)	0.67	0.22	1.05	0.23

Lin, Emanuel and Vanmarcke (2014) presented a review of hurricane risk analyses processes using physically- based approaches to tropical cyclones. Their main inference was that any estimated frequency of high-intensity storms is sensitive to how the tail of the probability distribution is modeled. Some predictive models also found that the storm’s outer radius obeyed a Lognormal Distribution.

Vickery, et al. (2000) made use of both land, coastal and sea-based measuring stations to develop a hurricane wind field model. The study is based on a nonlinear finite difference model of equations of motion of a hurricane including parameters ‘ r ’ (radial distance from the storms pressure center) and ‘ R_{max} ’ (radius to maximum winds). Error estimates for measurements were also made for simulated versus observed mean wind speeds.

Table 6. Parameters and Goodness of Fit of Distributions

No.	Variables	Form of Distribution	Model Parameters	Goodness of Fit	
				R ²	RMSE
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
1	Wind Speed (meters/sec)	GEV (Generalized Extreme Value)	$\epsilon = - 0.175$	0.9909	0.0308
			$\sigma = 0.934$		
			$\mu = 4.814$		
		Extreme Value Type 1	$\sigma = 0.791$	0.9933	0.0263
			$\mu = - 4.755$		
2	Thickness of Ice (mm)	GEV (Generalized Extreme Value)	$\epsilon = - 0.0646$	0.9533	0.0373
			$\sigma = 5.094$		
			$\mu = 10.272$		
		Extreme Value Type 1	$\sigma = 4.817$	0.9816	0.0391
			$\mu = - 10.170$		

Note: ϵ = shape parameter; σ = scale parameter; μ = position parameter

Jones (2002) suggests that wind speeds during freezing rain are typically moderate, ranging from 3 mps to 8 mps (6.7 mph to 17.9 mph). However, the ice that accretes on a wire may last for days or weeks after the end of the freezing rain. Therefore, these ice-laden wires may be exposed to high winds after the storm.

NIST Research on Wind

A significant amount of work on wind speeds, probabilistic analyses and modeling is performed at the NIST (National Institute of Standards and Technology) which was previously known as NBS (National Bureau of Standards). References such as NBS 577 (1980), NBS 868 (1975), NIST 500-301 (2023), NIST 898 (2004) and Simiu’s State-of-the-Art Volume (Simiu, 1995; Simiu, et al., 1995) contain valuable information on wind and hurricanes. NIST 898 (2004) contains a detailed discussion on various statistical techniques for high winds such as EVT Type 1,

EVT Type 2, Weibull and Reverse Weibull, Generalized Pareto and Generalized EV approaches.

Figure 3. Wind Speed V versus MRI Relationship

Important observations made in these studies are as follows:

1. Probability Distributions of extreme non-hurricane wind speeds are commonly assumed to have a Extreme Value Type 1 (Gumbel) Distribution but with parameters varying as a function of location.
2. Any coefficient of variation of a parameter is a function of both measurement and modeling errors and sampling errors, usually assumed contributing equally.
3. Non-Normal variables can be transformed into equivalent Normal ones before applying reliability formulations.

Figure 3, reproduced from Simiu et al (2012), shows a typical variation of wind speed with MRI.

Since ASCE standards now refer to a 100-year MRI, Figure 4 from NIST 500-301 is reproduced here showing both the wind speed contours for continental United States for a 100-year MRI as well as the error associated with those measurements.

Figure 4. 100-year Wind Speeds and Measurement Errors

Conclusions

In this paper, we discussed the phenomenon of ice and wind loads on transmission conductors, various statistical approaches to address their variations, and how they impact the definition of structural reliability of a utility structure. The discussions included distributions such as Normal (Gaussian), Lognormal, Weibull, Generalized Extreme Value and others. Inferences from this literature review include:

1. Incidence of radial ice on conductors can be taken as a Normal distribution with a COV ranging from 0.18 to 0.20.
 2. Extreme wind loads (hurricanes) are more difficult to assess since they are a function of location, terrain and means of synthesis of raw measured data at weather stations.
 3. COV of high winds varies between 0.08 and 0.10.
 4. Low-to-moderate winds – within 20 mph to 40 mph – can be considered to follow a Weibull Distribution. These speeds are associated with the NESC 250D loading condition (Table 1) where wind is concurrent with ice.
 5. Extreme or hurricane winds, from 90 mph to 150 mph (NESC 250C in Table 1), may be better represented with an Extreme Value Type 1 (EVT-1) distribution.
 6. Situations involving a combined or concurrent ice and wind are complex to deal with as they invoke different statistical distributions. One proposed approach is to derive an equivalent COV by converting the EVT-1 or Weibull (or other) into a Normal distribution and then combine the effects mathematically.
- Accurate statistical information on climatic phenomena helps engineers design strong and durable structures subject to such phenomena. Almost all weather events contain an implicit level of uncertainty which is often difficult to quantify and assess; but available design techniques do address that uncertainty via code provisions. For example, most design standards or codes prescribe overload factors for climatic

loads as a buffer against unexpected variation in imposed loads. Some utilities also ensure that their structures do not get loaded beyond 85% or 90% of their design capacity. This induces an additional factor of safety into the design.

Therefore, any research activity which helps supplement those factors with accurate statistical modeling of wind and ice is always welcome. Structural reliabilities determined for individual transmission structures can be used to evaluate the reliability of various segments of the electric grid and thereby that of the entire extended grid, transmission or distribution line. In this era of climate change, the ultimate goal of any research is to design a safe and reliable electric grid.

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Conflicts Of Interest

None.

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